

THE STRENGTH OF THE FAMILY AND GENDER EQUALITY IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to such issues as the family, women, girls, their development, science, education and upbringing, gender equality in the family, national consent, which are the basis and foundation of the future of the nation, national development. It is recognized that women's active participation of Uzbekistan in the life of state and society, their position in the family and carried out by the head of our state socially oriented women create the necessary opportunities for our daughter lived happily provided his rights and freedoms, increased moral and morale, performed their duties.*

Keywords: *family, gender equality, development, nationality, ideology, spiritual relations, intellectual relations, social approach, reproductive health, science, education.*

Introduction. The family is a high dwelling that preserves the continuity of a nation, a nation, ensures the development of national values, and determines the spiritual and physical development of a new generation. Family is one of the most beautiful miracles of the gift of nature, which is reflected in natural biological, economic, legal and spiritual relations inherent in humans. Family is a complex social group, formed as a result of a combination of biological, social, moral, ideological and spiritual relations. The family is a high dwelling that preserves the continuity of a nation, a nation, ensures the development of national values, and determines the spiritual and physical development of a new generation. Family is one of the most beautiful miracles of the gift of nature, which is reflected in natural biological, economic, legal and spiritual relations inherent in humans. Family is a complex social group, formed as a result of a combination of biological, social, moral, ideological and spiritual relations.

Research methodology

Pursuant to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2020 # up-5938 "on measures to improve the socio-spiritual atmosphere in society, further supporting the institution of mahalla and removal system work with families and women to a new level" and the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2020 # PP-4602 "on the organization of activities of the Ministry in support of makhalla and family of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Cabinet of Ministers, special attention is paid to creating conditions for the realization of their abilities and capabilities in various fields and industries, ensuring unconditional respect for their rights and legitimate interests, comprehensive support for motherhood and childhood, as well as strengthening the institution of the family. In addition, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke on September 23, 2020 at the 75th anniversary session of the United Nations General Assembly (UN), noting that among the areas of particular importance is the gender issue, and that " for us, the policy of gender equality has become a priority. The role of women in public administration is increasing. In the new parliament, the number of women deputies has doubled, "he noted the work on women's policy being carried out in our country. Indeed, in our country, the provision of all conditions for the full realization of women's opportunities has been raised to the level of state policy.

Today, the world community, correctly realizing the role of women in the development of humanity, is trying to create international mechanisms. The adoption of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination in the Field of Women's Rights by the UN General Assembly on December 18, 1979 is a testament to our opinion. This Convention is a fundamental document that clearly defines the problems associated with achieving the existing equality of women and men that is, ensuring gender equality, the practical use of women's rights.

The problems identified in the Convention are characterized by their versatility. In addition to clarifying the relevance of the problem of eliminating discrimination, which manifests itself in various forms, it reflects important provisions concerning the improvement of the status of women as an equal person, their political, socio-economic and cultural rights, and equality with men, and motherhood.

Women of Uzbekistan actively participate in the life of the state and society, and their position in the family is being strengthened. The socially-oriented policy pursued by the head of our state creates the necessary opportunities for a truly happy life for our women, the protection of their rights and freedoms, intellectual and spiritual growth, and the harmonious fulfillment of professional and family responsibilities.

The family is one of the oldest institutions of civil society, which has passed a difficult path of development. Man himself could not have lived in a primitive age. In the primitive era, man had a large family; the people in it were in close relations and were divided only into the categories of parents and children. The emergence of interest in the problem of the family is not accidental, because for several millennia, the family has been the basis of society, and they are in direct interaction.

According to the social approach — the family includes several components. The first of these components includes the qualification of the family as a union of people or a small social group, which expressed in the actions of people, that is, men and women, their children, towards a mutual single goal. Thus, the family is a united social organization of people.

One of the legally guaranteed family responsibilities is to prepare their children for starting a family. The "national training program" pays special attention to this issue:

- the family is the guardian, the successor of family traditions and spiritual and moral heritage;
- being the smallest part of society that ensures the growth of the child's cultural, aesthetic and other needs and a healthy lifestyle;
- the first coach who forms the foundations of the child's character; he is always an adviser, a guide for the younger generation in all spheres of life, " the message reads.

Thus, the strength of the family lies in its ability to strengthen the foundation of society, and its material and spiritual perfection is the basis of the well-being of the state and society. To implement all the issues related to family strength and gender equality, practical work was carried out in the following areas.

The family performs certain tasks even before the state. These are the functions of reproduction and upbringing. It is also considered among the important functions of the family in the organization of economic communication, comfort and recreation. The role of the family in the formation of social cohesion in society is difficult to overestimate. This complete organism is always developing, has passed a several stages in the process of its development. In it, that is, in the family, children come into the world, pass the first proverb, are brought up, get an education,

the main thing is that children themselves have the opportunity to create their own families, there was also a stage of the beginning of old age of elderly parents.

Conclusions and suggestions. The society has created all the conditions for the development of the family institution in accordance with modern statehood, including laws and regulations. During the ongoing reforms, the further improvement of legislative base in the field of family with the features and peculiarities of the legislation of individual countries of the world provide a solid basis for the further development of our society. In our republic, the achievement of "gender equality" is the key to further strengthening the position of women in society and at the same time strengthening the family, educating the younger generation at a high intellectual level, and ensuring the stability of society. In addition, it is necessary to ensure gender equality in society, improve the legal culture among women and men, prevent violence against women, domestic violence and expand opportunities to the further strengthen its legal foundations.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.Mirziyoyev's Resolution No. 201 "On the organization of activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the institution of the family".
2. Speech by President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 75th anniversary session of the United Nations General Assembly (UN) on September 23, 2020 .
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan"On the Ministry for the Support of the mahalla and the family". Decree No. PF-5938 of February 18, 2020
4. Women's rights. Women and elections. Women and Non-Governmental Organizations, Vol., 1999.
5. "Program of civil and legal education of women". Z. K. Ismailova. - Tashkent, Finance-2008